

The Relationship between Capital Structure and Financial Performance of Cement Industry in India

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Abstract

Purpose- This paper intends to discover the relationship between capital structure and financial performance of the cement industry by taken debt equity ratio and interest coverage ratio and Net Profit, Return on Asset, Return on Capital Employed and Return on Equity

Design/methodology/approach- It is an exploratory method of research where Debt Equity Ratio and Interest Coverage Ratio are taken as independent variables and Net Profit, ROA, ROE, and ROCE are taken as dependent variables. In the current research work data of 23 cement companies have been collected from different sources for 18 years from 2003-04 to 2020-21 and analyzed for descriptive, correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis to find out the relationship between capital structure and profitability of the selected cement companies.

Findings- Based on the correlation coefficient study shows the negative relationship between debt equity ratio and profitability and a positive relationship between interest coverage ratio and profitability. Based on the multiple regression analysis the study shows that multiple regression equation explains desired level of variability in Net Profit, ROA, ROE & ROCE.

Implications- This study has important implications for financial managers in taking capital structure decisions.

Key Words: - Debt Equity Ratio, Interest Coverage Ratio, Return on Asset. Return on Equity and Return on Capital employed.

1. Introduction

For all organization Capital Structure decisions are the most vital decisions because these decisions directly impact the profitability of any firm. Capital structure as defined by Panigrahi (2012) is the proportion between owner's funds and borrowed funds i.e., the long-term sources of funds. Owner's funds include Equity share Capital, Preference share capital, Reserves & Surpluses or retained earnings and Borrowed Funds includes long term debts like Debentures, Loan from Banks, and loan from other financial institutions Hasan & et.al (2014),

Capital structure decisions are of great importance because it determines the Risk factor and cost of capital. Determining the capital structure is an important decision that directly affects the company's profit. Therefore, care and attention should be taken when deciding on capital decision criteria. Velnampy & Niresh (2012)

The capital structure which optimizes the value of a firm is called optimum capital structure. In other words, when cost of capital is minimum, the capital structure is said to be maximum i.e., optimum and at this point of time the total value of the firm is also maximum Tailab (2014) Capital structure is influenced by some internal and external factors such as Size and nature of business, capital Gearing, cash position, Trading on Equity, Management's attitude, Age of Company, Government Policies, Market conditions and market competition (Mazumder (2017)

A company that has more debt in its capital structure leads to higher interest payments and thus lowers net worth profit. But on the other hand, debt capital also has a positive effect on profitability because interest payments are tax deductible, thereby reducing the overall tax burden. On the other hand, shareholders expect a return on their investment in the form of dividends. Compared to debt financing, equity affects profitability to a lesser extent with the payment of dividends only when the company is making a profit. Thus, a company with a high debt-to-equity ratio results in higher financial risk. Monga R (2018)

The purpose of this paper is to focus on how debt equity mix influences the performance of cement companies. An attempt has been made to analyze the capital structure with the help of Ratio Analysis, Descriptive analysis, Multiple regression analysis, and Correlation analysis by using the data from 2003-2004 to 2020-2021 of leading cement companies in India.

2. Literature Review

Velnampy & Niresh (2012) studied the connection between capital structure and productivity has been drawn and reasoned that capital structure affected adversely aside from debt to value and ROE. This study has been done on banks so extremely supportive for banking area. Handoo & Sharma (2014) focused on the determinants of capital structure and has been concluded that factors such as profitability, growth, asset tangibility, size, cost of debt, tax rate, and debt serving capacity have significant impact on the leverage structure chosen by firms in the Indian context. Kalyani and Mathur (2017) were chosen the Oil and Natural Gas Industry of India for the study. A sample of seven firms listed in NSE and BSE were selected for this study. The correlations and regression analyses were used to estimate the functions relating to profitability measured by Return on Assets and Net Profit Ratio with measures of capital structure. The study witness that Log sales, degree of operating leverage and growth of asset are significant variables in determining the profitability when dependent variables are ROA and log assets, degree of financial leverage, Log sales, degree of operating leverage and growth of asset have significant relationship with net profit ratio of the select firms from Oil and Natural Gas Industry of India. to contemplate the effect of

capital structure on productivity and discovered that the reliant elements like Return on resources, return on capital utilized, Return on Investment and Net benefit Ratio are profoundly affected by free factors like turnover of the firm, complete resources of the firm, debt administration limit, level of both working and money related influence.

Mazumder (2017) is being carried out on infrastructure companies listed on the Indian stock exchange. This research provides mixed results on the relationship between capital structure and firm performance. Data analysis was performed through ratio analysis and correlation matrices. Buferna & et.al (2005) concluded from their study that both the static trade-off theory and the agency cost theory are relevant theories while studying the determinants of capital structure. Rakesh (2013) studied the analysis of Capital Structure and Profitability of selected Companies listed at Bombay Stock Exchange. The study concluded that the relationship between capital structure and financial performance is negative because with the high degree of leverage the interest cost also increases which results in lower profitability.

Poddar and Mittal (2014)

This paper uses a panel data analysis method to examine the debt patterns of five Indian steel companies, including size, revenue, performance and interest rates. studied the determinants of Capital Structure and Profitability of chose of Selected Business Companies in Bombay Stock Exchange.

Panigrahi (2012) finds out the ways in which different companies at different times and in different institutional environments have financed their operations; and to identify possible implications of these financing patterns. Nenu & et.al (2018) studied the “Impact of Capital Structure on Risk and organization Performance” and determined that debt equity ratio is positively correlated and influence its performance with the size of the organization and the share price movements. Kurshev and Strebulaev (2015) studied the capital structure and firm size and founded the positive relation between the firm’s size and its financial leverage. The analysis of economy demonstrates that in cross-section, the relationship between leverage and size is positive and thus fixed costs of financing contribute to the explanation of the stylized size–leverage relationship.

Aishwarya & et.al (2020) found that ROCE, ROLT and RONW have a positive impact on the company's debt-equity ratio and interest rate (i.e. capital structure), while GP, OP and ROA are negatively related. This study also reveals the significant impact of capital structure on profitability. Jain & et.al (2017) showed that there is a significant relationship between the ratio of short-term debt to total working capital and ROA (return on total assets). Similar results were obtained for the ratio of total debt to total working capital and return on assets. However, in terms of the relationship between long-term debt and ROA, the results show a positive but insignificant relationship between the two.

Table 1: Review of past studies with respect to multiple regression analysis

S.N.	Author and Year	Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	Findings of the Studies
1	Abor (2005)	Short term debt Long term dent Total debt	ROE	The results show that there is a significant relationship between the ratio of short-term debt to total assets and return on equity.
2	Azhagaiah & Gavoury (2011)	Total Debt to Total Asset Expense to Income Ratio Debt Equity Ratio Current Ratio	ROA ROCE	This research has proven that there is a one-to-one relationship between capital structure variables and profitability variables, return on assets (ROA) and return on capital employed (ROCE). Capital structure is significantly influencing the profitability and by increasing the financial leverage tends to lower the profitability.

3	Ali & et.al (2016)	Short term debt to Asset Ratio Long term debt to Asset Ratio Funded Capital Ratio Funded Debt Ratio Current Debt Ratio Funded Asset Ratio Sales Growth	ROA	The results show that the independent variables of the automobile industry have positive and negative variables, except for CDR companies, other variables have a negative impact on benefits. In the cement sector, while LTDTA and CDR negatively affect the profit, STDTA, FCR, FDR, FAR and sales growth affect the profit positively.
4	Addae (2013)	Short term debt Long term dent Total debt	ROE	The results revealed that, there is a statistically significant positive relationship between profitability and short-term debt and a significantly negative relationship between profitability and long-term debt. However, the results revealed a statistically negative relationship between profitability and total debt
5	Aishwarya & et.al (2020)	Gross Profit Operating Profit Return on Asset Return on Capital Employed Return on Long term Funds. Return on Net worth.	Debt Equity Ratio Interest Coverage ratio	The study found that ROCE, ROLT and RONW have a positive impact on the company's debt-equity ratio and interest rate (i.e. capital structure), while GP, OP and ROA are negatively related. This study also reveals the significant impact of capital structure on profitability.
6	Ahmad (2014)	Debt Equity Ratio Debt Ratio Interest coverage Ratio	ROE	The results implied that profitability is significantly related to capital structure. Specifically, profitability was inversely related to the amount of liability in a company's capital structure.
7	Hasan & et.al (2014)	Short term debt Long term dent Total debt	EPS ROE ROA Tobin's Q	It is found that EPS is significantly positively related to short-term debt while significantly negatively related to long-term debt.
8	Tailab (2014)	Short term debt	ROA	The study found that total debt had a negative impact on ROE and ROA, while sales only

		Long term dent Total debt Debt to Equity	ROE	had a negative impact on the ROE of American companies. However, short-term debt has a positive impact on ROE.
9	Nasimi (2016)	Debt to Equity Interest Coverage Ratio	ROA ROE ROIC	Research shows that capital structure has an impact on company's performance. The findings show that the higher the loan amount, the more tax advantage (tax shield) the company receives. Therefore, for the business to achieve its goals, the directors and managers of the company must agree on the capital structure.
10	Yegon &et.al (2014)	Short term debt to total asset Long term debt to total asset Total debt to total asset	ROE	According to research, short-term debt has a positive relationship with profits. Long-term debt has a negative relationship with profits. The results showed no significant relationship between total debt and profitability
Source: Author (s) compilation				

Table 2: Review of past studies with respect to Correlation analysis

S.No.	Author and Year	Variables	Findings of the Studies
1	Azhagaiah & Gavoury (2011)	Total Debt to Total Asset Expense to Income Ratio Debt Equity Ratio Current Ratio ROA ROCE	Negative relation is found between variables. CS has a significant influence on Profitability and increase in the cs use of debt fund intends to reduce the net profit of the firms listed cs it in Bombay Stock Exchange in India.
2	Singh &Singh (2016)	Debt Equity Ratio Debt to Total Fund Ratio Gross Profit Ratio Return on Capital Return on Equity	Based on correlation coefficient, study found a significant negative relationship between debt and profitability i.e. companies with higher proportion of debt tend to have low profitability.
3	Velnampy & Niresh	Debt Equity Debt to Total Fund	The analysis results show that, in addition to the positive relationship between debt-equity swaps and return on equity,

	(2012)	Net Profit ROCE ROE Net Interest Margin	there is also a negative relationship between capital structure and profitability.
4	Nasimi (2016)	Debt to Equity Interest Coverage Ratio ROA ROE ROIC	The results show that the interest coverage ratio has a positive impact on ROA, ROE and ROIC, while DE has a positive impact on ROE but a negative impact on ROA and ROIC.
5	Chisti & et.al (2013)	Debt to Equity Ratio Debt to Asset Ratio Interest Coverage Ratio Gross Profit Net Profit Operating Profit ROCE ROI	Debt to Equity ratio is negatively correlated to profitability ratios which imply that if the debt content is increased aggressively, it will adversely impact the profitability. Debt to Assets ratio and Interest coverage ratio are positively and significantly correlated with the profitability ratio.
6.	Jain & et.al (2017)	Short Term debt Long Term Debt Capital Employed Return on Total Asset Return on Asset	The results show that there is a significant relationship between the ratio of short-term debt to total working capital and ROA (return on total assets). Similar results were obtained for the ratio of total debt to total working capital and return on assets. However, in terms of the relationship between long-term debt and ROA, the results show a positive but insignificant relationship between the two.
7.	Zafar & et.al (2016)	Short Term Liability to Asset Ratio Long Term Liability to Asset Ratio Total Liability to Total Equity Total Liability to Total Asset	Findings of the study authenticated a positive relationship between determinants of capital structure and performance of banking industry.

		ROA	
8.	Rahman & et.al (2019)	ROA ROE EPS Debt to Equity Ratio Debt Ratio Equity Ratio	This study found that debt ratio and equity ratio have a positive relationship with ROA, but debt/equity ratio has a negative effect for ROA, while debt/equity ratio is significant. and a significant impact on ROA. This article also shows the negative impact of ROA. This article also shows that Law has a positive impact on ROE, while the debt/equity ratio has a positive impact, but the debt/value ratio balance has a significant and negative impact on ROE. Finally, the debt-to-equity ratio has a significant and negative impact on EPS. The results of this study will negatively affect the earnings per share statement.
9.	Mazumder (2017)	Debt Equity ROE ROA ROCE Interest coverage ratio	This study found that there is a positive correlation between Debt Equity and Return on Capital Employed. There is a positive correlation between Debt Equity and Return on Equity & Return on Capital Employed and Return on Equity
10.	Singh (2019)	Total liabilities to Total Asset Total Equity to Total Asset ROA ROE	The relationships indicate that debt ratios have a negative impact on ROA and ROE, while equity ownership has a direct impact on both performances. ROA and ROE have a positive relationship with each other. TETA has a positive correlation with ROA, but TLTA has a negative correlation. LIQ is negatively correlated with TANG, BR is positively correlated with TAX and LIQ, and IR is negatively correlated with TAX.
Source: Author (s) compilation			

Though there are many studies have been undertaken as discussed above but no study has been done so far in respect of the selected variables, time zone and selected cement companies. The main objective of the present study is to focus on the impact of capital structure on profitability of cement industry in India.

4. Research Methodology

This section presents the context of the study, research design, research questions, objectives of the study, hypothesis of the study, data, description of variables, and methods of data analysis.

4.1 Context

The relationship between capital structure and profitability has received much attention in the finance literature. Research on the impact of capital structure on profitability will help us to understand possible problems in performance linked with capital structure. Today's business world must operate in a complex and competitive business environment. Therefore, such research will help in choosing the investment model to achieve a high level of business profitability. This study provides statistical analysis to reveal whether there is a relationship between capital structure and profitability.

4.2 Research design

It includes research questions, research objectives, data collected and analysed to achieve the research objectives and answer the research questions.

4.2.1 Research Questions

In view of the above background, the current study attempts to answer the following questions.

- (i) what are the components of capital structure?
- (ii) Whether the debt equity ratio influence the financial performance of any organization
- (iii) what is the relationship between interest coverage ratio and the financial performance?
- (iv) How the financial performance can be measured?

This study is based on secondary data which has been collected through annual reports of the companies, NSE & BSE websites.

4.2.2 Objectives of the study

The objectives of the current study are:

- (i) To review the past work of on the relationship of capital structure on profitability of cement Industry.
- (ii) To analyze the relationship between capital structure (Debt Equity Ratio and Interest Coverage Ratio) and profitability (Net Profit, Return on Asset, Return on Capital Employed and Return on Equity) of cement companies in India.
- (iii) To suggest strategies for enhance profitability in cement industry.

4.2.3 Hypothesis of the study

H0₁: There is no significant impact of independent variables on Net Profit

H0₂: There is no significant impact of independent variables on Return on Asset

H0₃: There is no significant impact of independent variables on Return on Equity

H0₄: There is no significant impact of independent variables on Return on capital employed.

4.2.4 Data

The sample contains data of 23 selected Indian cement companies listed on the National Stock exchange and Bombay stock exchange, sourced from the annual reports of the companies and from websites such as money control and business standard. The data covers a period of 18 years from 2003-04 to 2020-21. The companies have been selected based on availability of data. Data was processed through the SPSS 25 version.

To find out the relationship between capital structure and profitability, correlation and Multiple regression analysis have been done.

After study and analyse the work done by the previous researchers Debt Equity ratio and Interest Coverage ratio has been chosen to represent the capital structure as independent Variable and to measure the financial performance of the selected cement companies Net Profit, ROA, ROE, and ROCE has been taken as dependent variables.

4.3 Brief on dependent and independent variables

Based on the study of previous researchers a few important dependent and independent variables have been chosen.

Debt equity ratio and interest coverage ratio have been taken as independent variables and Net Profit, ROA, ROE, and ROCE taken as dependent variables.

Table 3: Computation of dependent and independent variables

S.No.	Variable	Type	Computation
1	Debt Equity Ratio	Independent	Long Term Debts/Total Equity
2	Interest Coverage Ratio	Independent	Interest Coverage Ratio = EBITDA/ Interest
3	Net Profit	Dependent	Net Profit/Net Sales*100
4	ROA	Dependent	Net Income/Total Asset
5	ROE	Dependent	Net Income/Shareholders Equity
6	ROCE	Dependent	EBIT/Capital Employed

Source: Monga R (2018), Singh and Bagga (2019), Nasimi (2016), Chisti (2013)

4.4 Methods for data analysis

To accomplish the objectives data has been collected from the secondary sources by going through annual reports of selected cement companies and various websites. Descriptive statistics have been used to describe the behavior of the variables, Ratio Analysis has been done to calculate the independent and dependent variables such as Debt Equity ratio, Interest coverage ratio, Net Profit ratio, ROA, ROE, and ROCE. Correlation and multiple regression analysis have been carried out to identify the relationship between capital structure and profitability.

5. Results and Discussions

5.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 4 shows that the mean score, Minimum value, Maximum value, and Range of Debt equity is 1.6, -3.94, 153.81, 157.76 respectively with a standard deviation of 8.29 and Std. error of 0.41. The mean score, Minimum value, Maximum value, and Range of Interest Coverage Ratio is 12.63, -1.80, 238.18, 239.98 respectively with a standard deviation of 21.41 and Std. error of 1.05. The mean score, Minimum value, Maximum value, and Range of Net Profit Ratio is 104.28, -70.12, 40300, 40370.12 respectively with a standard deviation of 1980.32 and Std. error of 97.33. The mean score, Minimum value, Maximum value, and Range of Return on Asset Ratio is 6.64, -16.01, 89.66, 105.67 respectively with a standard deviation of 8.17 and Std. error of 0.40. The mean score, Minimum value, Maximum value, and Range of Return on Equity Ratio is 3.53, -2488.63, 1313, 3801.63 respectively with a standard deviation of 166.38 and Std. error of 8.18. The mean score, Minimum value, Maximum value, and Range of Return on Capital Employed Ratio is 3.53, -123.58, 545.92, 669.50 respectively with a standard deviation of 28.89 and Std. error of 1.42.

Table:4 Descriptive Statistics of 23 selected Cement companies

Variables	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	S.D.	SE
No. of observations (414)						
Debt Equity Ratio	1.60	-3.94	153.81	157.76	8.29	0.41
Interest Coverage Ratio	12.63	-1.80	238.18	239.98	21.41	1.05
Net Profit	104.28	-70.12	40300.00	40370.12	1980.32	97.33
Return on Asset	6.64	-16.01	89.66	105.67	8.17	0.40

Return on Equity	3.53	-2488.63	1313.00	3801.63	166.38	8.18
Return on Capital Employed	10.69	-123.58	545.92	669.50	28.89	1.42

5.2 Multiple Regression Model

This section presents the results of multiple regression analysis for individual cement companies. The multiple regression analysis is done to assess the impact of capital structure on profitability as mentioned earlier. The functional form of multiple regression equation is as under

$$Y=a+b_1*X_1+b_2*X_2$$

where Y= Net Profit, X₁= Debt Equity Ratio and X₂= Interest Coverage Ratio

The sample null hypothesis to be tested as part of multiple regression analysis are as under

H₀: There is no significant impact of capital structure on profitability of Ultratech Cement.

H₁: There is significant impact of capital structure on profitability of Ultratech Cement.

Similarly, hypothesis will be tested for all 23 companies selected in this study. The results of multiple regression analysis in the form of values of regression coefficient, adjusted R² and p-values are shown in table 5 to table 8.

Table 5: Multiple Regression Analysis between Debt Equity Ratio & Interest Coverage Ratio and Net Profit for selected cement companies

S.N.	Name of the company	Multiple Regression Equation			Adjusted R ² (p-values)
1	UltraTech Cement	7.030	-2.605*X1 (0.050) *	+0.482*X2 (0.000) *	0.699* (0.000)
2	Ambuja Cements	11.397	+11.185*X1 (0.091)	+0.089*X2 (0.234)	0.080 (0.210)
3	Shree Cement	11.618	-4.220*X1 (0.148)	+ 0.210*X2 (0.101)	0.104 (0.171)
4	ACC Limited	1.264	+15.612*X1 (0.009) *	+ 0.284*X2 (0.035) *	0.300* (0.027)
5	RAMCO Cements Limited	5.702	+0.909*X1 (0.628)	+0.468*X2 (0.016)	0.300* (0.027)
6	JK Cement	16883.413	-5238.242*X1 (0.587)	-2193.630*X2 (0.178)	0.030 (0.311)
7	JK Laxmi Cement	0.603	-1.950*X1 (0.054)	+1.986*X2 (0.001) *	0.518* (0.002)
8	Heidelberg Materials	0.0828	-0.319*X1 (0.388)	+ 0.185*X2 (0.018) *	0.305* (0.026)

9	India Cements	2.872	-1.678*X1 (0.470)	+0.901*X2 (0.001) *	0.790* (0.001)
10	HIL Limited	6.012	-4.685*X1 (0.137)	+0.098*X2 (0.237)	0.254* (0.043)
11	Jai Prakash Associated Limited	-10.637	-12.742*X1 (0.034) *	+13.585*X2 (0.000) *	0.680* (0.000)
12	Ramco Industries Limited	5.278	+0.372*X1 (0.796)	+0.289*X2 (0.028) *	0.232 (0.054)
13	Sagar Cements Limited	4.125	-3.746*X1 (0.500)	+0.903*X2 (0.008) *	0.330* (0.019)
14	KCP Cement	0.254	+0.769*X1 (0.811)	+0.925*X2 (0.000) *	0.831* (0.000)
15	Sanghi Cements Limited	4.974	+1.051*X1 (0.664)	+0.075*X2 (0.858)	-0.119 (0.907)
16	Shree Digvijay Cement Company Limited	1.495	+4.428*X1 (0.384)	+0.096*X2 (0.248)	0.059 (0.247)
17	Visaka Industries Ltd.	-1.249	+3.244*X1 (0.01) *	+0.781*X2 (0.000) *	0.794* (0.000)
18	NCL Industries Ltd.	135.561	-1.214*X1 (0.918)	-2.322*X2 (0.612)	-0.004 (0.877)
19	Mangalam Cement Limited	21.487	-21.887*X1 (0.029) *	+0.056*X2 (0.509)	0.261* (0.040)
20	Deccan Cements Ltd.	6.515	-1.109*X1 (0.522)	+0.144*X2 (0.000) *	0.544* (0.001)
21	Shree Keshav Cements and Infra Limited	1.344	-0.205*X1 (0.000) *	+0.225*X2 (0.719)	0.679* (0.000)
22	Prism Johnson Limited	11.212	-6.905*X1 (0.010) *	+0.076*X2 (0.004) *	0.809* (0.000)
23	Kesoram Industries Ltd.	-3.596	-0.262*X1 (0.014) *	+13.72*X2 (0.001) *	0.669* (0.000)
*All these values are significant as p-value is <= 0.05. The p-values are parentheses.					
Source: data collected from annual reports and values calculated through MS Excel and SPSS					

It can be inferred from the results given in table 5 that two variables representing capital structure could not reveal significant variability of Net Profit for six companies as p-values are greater than 0.05. These companies are Ambuja Cement (0.210), Shree Cement (0.171), RAMCO Industries Ltd. (0.054), JK Cement (0.311), Shree

Digvijay Cement Company Ltd. (0.247), NCL Industries Ltd. (0.877). For the remaining 17 companies' multiple regression equation explains desired level of variability in Net Profitability. In addition, it is further concluded that for most cement companies (14) the regression coefficient of Debt Equity Ratio is negative. It means it is negatively impacting Net Profit and for most companies (21) the regression coefficient of Interest Coverage Ratio is positive. It means there is a positive relationship between Interest coverage Ratio and Net profit. It is also inferred that maximum value of adjusted R² is 0.831 (KCP Cement) and minimum value is -0.004 (NCL Industries Ltd.).

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis between Debt Equity Ratio & Interest Coverage Ratio and ROA for selected cement companies

S.No	Name of the company	Multiple Regression Equation			Adjusted R ² (p-values)
1	UltraTech Cement	0.867	+0.298X1 (0.807)	+0.584X2 (0.000)	0.684* (0.000)
2	Ambuja Cements	5.373	+11.683X1 (0.169)	+0.115X2 (0.241)	0.027 (0.319)
3	Shree Cement	8.503	-1.999X1 (.0381)	+0.121X2 (0.229)	-0.012 (0.426)
4	ACC Limited	3.690	+10.117X1 (0.069)	+0.166X2 (0.196)	0.097 (0.182)
5	RAMCO Cements Limited	0.850	+1.373X1 (0.247)	+0.412X2 (0.002)	0.462* (0.004)
6	JK Cement	-10.828	+6.346X1 (0.119)	+3.014X2 (0.000)	0.627* (0.000)
7	JK Laxmi Cement	7.273	-2.737X1 (0.013)	+1.037X2 (0.051)	0.353* (0.015)
8	Heidelberg Materials	6.548	-0.217X1 (0.614)	+0.179X2 (0.044)	0.187* (0.082)
9	India Cements	2.434	-2.467X1 (0.423)	+0.974X2 (0.003)	0.481* (0.003)
10	HIL Limited	10.755	-7.041X1 (0.266)	+0.330X2 (0.060)	0.328* (0.020)
11	Jai Prakash Associated Limited	-2.414	-1.454X1 (0.093)	+2.595X2 (0.000)	0.790* (0.000)
12	Ramco Industries Limited	3.520	+0.503X1 (0.638)	+0.206X2 (0.033)	0.196 (0.076)
13	Sagar Cements Limited	1.947	-2.392X1	+0.794X2	0.651*

			(0.371)	(0.000)	(0.000)
14	KCP Cement	0.082	-0.005X1 (0.999)	+0.731X2 (0.000)	0.830* (0.000)
15	Sanghi Cements Limited	1.171	+0.919X1 (0.352)	+0.132X2 (0.435)	-0.053 (0.577)
16	Shree Digvijay Cement Company Limited	3.410	+4.004X1 (0.563)	+0.098X2 (0.382)	-0.026 (0.473)
17	Visaka Industries Ltd.	0.524	+1.990X1 (0.045)	+0.877X2 (0.000)	0.781* (0.000)
18	NCL Industries Ltd.	5.008	-0.158X1 (0.000)	+0.150X2 (0.000)	0.185* (0.000)
19	Mangalam Cement Limited	36.546	-40.176X1 (0.016)	-0.063X2 (0.653)	0.243* (0.049)
20	Deccan Cements Ltd.	8.775	-4.197X1 (0.001)	+0.084X2 (0.001)	0.666* (0.000)
21	Shree Keshav Cements and Infra Limited	1.457	-0.072X1 (0.001)	+0.071X2 (0.824)	0.485* (0.003)
22	Prism Johnson Limited	11.453	-7.041X1 (0.035)	+0.078X2 (0.016)	0.722* (0.000)
23	Kesoram Industries Ltd.	-3.021	-0.202X1 (0.012)	+1.329X2 (0.000)	0.751* (0.000)
*All these values are significant as p-value is ≤ 0.05 . The p-values are parentheses.					
Source: data collected from annual reports and values calculated through MS Excel and SPSS					

It can be inferred from the results given in table 6 that two variables representing capital structure could not reveal significant variability of ROA for seven companies as p-values are greater than 0.05. These companies are Ambuja Cement (0.319), Shree Cement (0.426), ACC (0.182), Heidelberg Materials (0.082), Ramco Industries Limited (0.076), Sanghi Cement Ltd. (0.577), and Shree Digvijay Cement Company Ltd. (0.473). For the remaining 16 companies' multiple regression equation explains desired level of variability in ROA. In addition, it is further concluded that for most cement companies (14) the regression coefficient of Debt Equity Ratio is negative. It means it is negatively impacting ROA and for most companies (22) the regression coefficient of Interest Coverage Ratio is positive. It means it positively impacts ROA. It is also inferred that maximum value of adjusted R^2 is 0.830 (KCP Cement) and minimum value is -0.053 (Sanghi Cement Ltd.).

Table 7: Multiple Regression Analysis between Debt Equity Ratio & Interest Coverage Ratio and ROE for selected cement companies

S.N	Name of the company	Multiple Regression Equation			Adjusted R ² (p-values)
1	UltraTech Cement	-3.519	+5.697*X1 (0.132)	+1.358*X2 (0.000) *	0.520* (0.002)
2	Ambuja Cements	6.827	+25.024*X1 (0.051)	+0.156*X2 (0.277)	0.128 (0.139)
3	Shree Cement	8.312	+10.369*X1 (0.075)	+0.267*X2 (0.275)	0.243* (0.049)
4	ACC Limited	4.243	+28.256*X1 (0.005) *	+0.274*X2 (0.204)	0.370* (0.012)
5	RAMCO Cements Limited	8.080	+11.619*X1 (0.009) *	+1.275*X2 (0.003) *	0.402* (0.008)
6	JK Cement	1.835	-1.646*X1 (0.755)	+3.300*X2 (0.001) *	0.675* (0.000)
7	JK Laxmi Cement	-3.744	-4.032*X1 (0.093)	+4.781*X2 (0.001) *	0.503* (0.002)
8	Heidelberg Materials	5.383	-0.268*X1 (0.470)	+0.229*X2 (0.005) *	0.396* (0.009)
9	India Cements	0.447	-5.897*X1 (0.530)	+2.751*X2 (0.006) *	0.425* (0.006)
10	HIL Limited	14.975	-8.796*X1 (0.318)	+0.228*X2 (0.331)	0.110 (0.163)
11	Jai Prakash Associated Limited	-10.196	-9.145*X1 (0.072)	+12.688*X2 (0.000) *	0.718* (0.000)
12	Ramco Industries Limited	6.792	+2.027*X1 (0.378)	+0.296*X2 (0.135)	0.029 (0.313)
13	Sagar Cements Limited	-0.032	+1.822*X1 (0.724)	+1.599*X2 (0.000) *	0.648* (0.000)
14	KCP Cement	-0.483	+2.901*X1 (0.636)	+1.505*X2 (0.000) *	0.798* (0.000)
15	Sanghi Cements Limited	4974	+1.051*X1 (0.664)	+0.075*X2 (0.858)	0.114 (0.907)

16	Shree Digvijay Cement Company Limited	6.898	+63.135*X1 (0.000) *	-0.027*X2 (0.891)	0.610* (0.000)
17	Visaka Industries Ltd.	-1.607	+11.276*X1 (0.001) *	+1.570*X2 (0.000) *	0.583* (0.001)
18	NCL Industries Ltd.	31.913	-17.380*X1 (0.000) *	-0.046*X2 (0.813)	0.748* (0.000)
19	Mangalam Cement Limited	442.117	-529.464*X1 (0.031) *	-2694*X2 (0.207)	0.193* (0.078)
20	Deccan Cements Ltd.	11.738	-2.895*X1 (0.235)	+0.215*X2 (0.000) *	0.596* (0.000)
21	Shree Keshav Cements and Infra Limited	57.192	-16.464*X1 (0.000) *	-3.394*X2 (0.412)	0.997* (0.000)
22	Prism Johnson Limited	23.714	-13.268*X1 (0.058) *	+0.068*X2 (0.280)	0.492* (0.002)
23	Kesoram Industries Ltd.	98.656	27.701*X1 (0.000) *	--5.525*X2 (0.639)	0.811* (0.000)
*All these values are significant as p-value is <= 0.05. The p-values are parentheses.					
Source: data collected from annual reports and values calculated through MS Excel and SPSS					

It can be inferred from the results given in table 7 that two variables representing capital structure could not reveal significant variability of ROE for four companies as p-values are greater than 0.05. These companies are Ambuja Cement (0.139), HIL Ltd. (0.163), RAMCO Industries Ltd. (0.313), Sanghi Cement Ltd. (0.907). For the remaining 19 companies' multiple regression equation explains desired level of variability in ROE. In addition, it is further concluded that for most cement companies (11) the regression coefficient of Debt Equity Ratio is negative. It means it is negatively impacting ROE and for most companies (18) the regression coefficient of Interest Coverage Ratio is positive. It means it positively impacts ROE. It is also inferred that maximum value of adjusted R² is 0.997 (Shree Keshav Cements and Infra Limited) and minimum value is 0.029 (RAMCO Industries Ltd.).

Table 8: Multiple Regression Analysis between Debt Equity Ratio & Interest Coverage Ratio and ROE for selected cement companies

S.N.	Name of the company	Multiple Regression Equation			Adjusted R ² (p-values)
1	UltraTech Cement	7.036	-2.148X1 (0.249)	+0.518X2 (0.004)	0.514* (0.002)
2	Ambuja Cements	8.272	+9.801X1 (0.305)	+0.132X2 (0.239)	-0.011 (0.426)
3	Shree Cement	12.408	-3.162X1	+0.131X2	-0.030

			(0.317)	(0.339)	(0.487)
4	ACC Limited	6.993	+12.396X1 (0.113)	+0.237X2 (0.194)	0.052 (0.262)
5	RAMCO Cements Limited	3.199	+0.223X1 (0.891)	+0.635X2 (0.001)	0.594* (0.000)
6	JK Cement	-10.828	+6.346X1 (0.119)	+3.014X2 (0.000)	0.627* (0.000)
7	JK Laxmi Cement	7.273	-2.737X1 (0.013)	+1.037X2 (0.051)	0.353* (0.015)
8	Heidelberg Materials	6.548	-0.217X1 (0.614)	+ 0.179X2 (0.044)	0.187* (0.082)
9	India Cements	2.434	-2.467X1 (0.423)	+0.974X2 (0.003)	0.736* (0.003)
10	HIL Limited	10.755	-7.041X1 (0.266)	+0.330X2 (0.060)	0.328* (0.020)
11	Jai Prakash Associated Limited	0.504	-2.337X1 (0.031)	+2.651X2 (0.000)	0.718* (0.000)
12	Ramco Industries Limited	7.392	-1.409X1 (0.408)	+0.440X2 (0.006)	0.485* (0.003)
13	Sagar Cements Limited	8.118	-4.261X1 (0.395)	+1.360X2 (0.000)	0.606* (0.000)
14	KCP Cement	2.597	-1.153X1 (.840)	+0.990X2 (0.001)	0.657* (0.000)
15	Sanghi Cements Limited	3.518	-0.058X1 (0.959)	+0.050X2 (0.799)	-0.126 (0.954)
16	Shree Digvijay Cement Company Limited	-6.522	+46.995X1 (0.012)	+0.094X2 (.0728)	0.308* (0.025)
17	Visaka Industries Ltd.	1.953	-1.403X1 (0.601)	+1.622X2 (0.000)	0.658* (0.000)
18	NCL Industries Ltd.	8.540	-0.045X1 (0.790)	+0.176X2 (0.008)	0.013* (0.027)
19	Mangalam Cement Limited	194.732	-27.263X1 (0.023)	-1.107X2 (0.200)	0.218 (0.062)
20	Deccan Cements Ltd.	12.731	-6.595X1	+0.106X2	0.577*

			(0.002)	(0.006)	(0.001)
21	Shree Keshav Cements and Infra Limited	6.949	+0.032X1 (0.273)	-0.583X2 (0.257)	0.085 (0.200)
22	Prism Johnson Limited	28.413	-12.816X1 (0.052)	+0.091X2 (0.134)	0.573* (0.001)
23	Kesoram Industries Ltd.	-6.092	+0.193X1 (0.252)	+2.277X2 (0.001)	0.458* (0.004)
*All these values are significant as p-value is <= 0.05. The p-values are parentheses.					
Source: data collected from annual reports and values calculated through MS Excel and SPSS					

It can be inferred from the results given in table 8 that two variables representing capital structure could not reveal significant variability of ROCE for seven companies as p-values are greater than 0.05. These companies are Ambuja Cement (0.426), Shree Cement (0.487), ACC (0.262), Heidelberg Materials (0.082), Sanghi Cement Ltd. (0.954), Manglam Cement Ltd. (0.062) and Shree Keshav Cements and Infra Limited (0.2). For the remaining 16 companies' multiple regression equation explains desired level of variability in ROCE. In addition, it is further concluded that for most cement companies (16) the regression coefficient of Debt Equity Ratio is negative. It means it is negatively impacting ROCE and for most companies (21) the regression coefficient of Interest Coverage Ratio is positive. It means it positively impacts ROCE. It is also inferred that maximum value of adjusted R² is 0.736 (India Cement) and minimum value is -0.126 (Sanghi Cement Ltd.).

5.3 Correlation Analysis

This section presents the results of the Correlation between capital structure (Debt Equity Ratio and Interest Coverage Ratio) and profitability (Net Profit, ROA, ROE, and ROCE) of selected cement companies. The Correlation coefficient is calculated to assess the impact of capital structure on profitability as mentioned earlier.

Table 9: Correlation Coefficient between all the Variables

	Debt Equity	Interest Coverage Ratio	Net Profit	ROA	ROE	ROCE
Debt Equity	1	-0.076 (0.121)	-0.003 (0.949)	-0.190** (0.000)	-0.866** (0.000)	-0.023 (0.641)
Interest Coverage Ratio	-0.076 (0.121)	1	-0.0025 (0.616)	0.404** (0.000)	0.060 (0.221)	0.131** (0.007)
Net Profit	-0.003 (0.949)	-0.025 (0.616)	1	-0.036 (0.461)	0.001 (0.986)	-0.016 (0.743)
ROA	-0.190** (0.000)	0.404** (0.000)	-0.036 (0.461)	1	0.408** (0.000)	0.660** (0.000)
ROE	-0.866** (0.000)	0.060 (0.221)	0.001 (0.986)	0.408** (0.000)	1	0.381** (0.000)

ROCE	-0.023 (0.641)	0.131** (0.007)	-0.016 (0.743)	0.660** (0.000)	0.381** (0.000)	1
Source: data collected from annual reports and values calculated through MS Excel and SPSS						

The result of correlation coefficient is presented in table 9. It can be inferred from the table that there is a negative relationship between Debt Equity Ratio and Net Profit (-0.003), ROA (-0.190), ROE (-0.866) and ROCE (-0.023) and a positive correlation exist between Interest Coverage Ratio and ROA (0.404), ROE (0.060) & ROCE (0.131). Interest Coverage Ratio is negatively related to Net Profit (-0.076).

6. Conclusion

This study aims to analyze the impact of capital structure on Profitability using a sample of 23 listed cement companies in India for the period 2004 to 2021. To explore the relationship between capital structure and Financial performance the effect the study consists of two independent and four dependent variables.

Based on the multiple regression analysis the study shows that multiple regression equation explains desired level of variability in Net Profit, ROA, ROE & ROCE for most of the companies. It is further concluded that for most cement companies the regression coefficient of Debt Equity Ratio is negative. It means it is negatively impacting profitability and for most companies the regression coefficient of Interest Coverage Ratio is positive. It means it positively impacts profitability.

Based on correlation analysis of the study, there exists a negative relationship between debt equity and Profitability (Net Profit, ROA, ROE & ROCE) and there is a positive relationship between Interest Coverage Ratio and profitability except Net Profit. Tailab (2014), Chisti & et.al (2013)

7. Suggestions

The results of the study show that debt has a negative relationship with the financial performance of cement production companies. The recommendation for the cement sector is to use equity capital instead of debt, as its revenue is not sufficient to cover its liabilities arising from debt. The share of debt in its finances should be less and it should rely more on equity capital. All these suggestions are in response to the current situation where the cement industry is facing losses and debts that increase operating costs, ultimately leading to many burdens and losses. Now, to support the development of this business, the government needs to create policies that will ensure that the cost of debt is low. If the company uses debt, it must pay the cost of using debt and the benefits of this will have a positive impact on its profits.

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